

Usd, Gold and Real Estate Price Change Rates in Metropolitans in the Last 10 Years in Turkiye

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Abstract

The United States saw the bursting of the housing bubble, a crisis in the subprime mortgage market, and the beginning of an economic recession during the latter part of 2007 and into the beginning of 2008. Shortly after the beginning of the global financial crisis in September 2008, Turkiye saw a dramatic decrease in employment as well as economic production (Tanrivermis, 2020). This happened shortly after the crisis began. In spite of the fact that the repercussions of the mortgage crisis are no longer being felt, the globe is now coping with a new crisis as a direct result of the breakout of COVID-19.

Limitedness

The subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

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Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

A housing bubble bust, a crisis in the subprime mortgage industry, and the beginning of an economic recession all occurred in the United States during the latter half of 2007 and the beginning of 2008, respectively. Later on, it had an effect on the economy of the whole globe, which led to the worldwide recession known as the worldwide recession or the Global Financial Crisis that took place in 2007-2008 (Yildirim, 2020). Both employment and economic production in Turkiye saw a significant drop not long after the beginning of the global financial crisis in September 2008 (Tanrivermis, 2020). This event took place in Turkiye. In spite of the fact that the repercussions of the mortgage crisis are no longer being felt, the globe is now coping with a new crisis as a direct result of the breakout of COVID-19. On the other hand, economists have discovered that the current COVID-19 issue has significant similarities with the problem of Global Finance. (Strauss-Kahn, 2020) Identifies a number of parallels between the two crises, including unpredictability, collapse, and governmental responses aimed at reducing the impact of shocks on the economy. The COVID-19 pandemic, which first appeared in the year 2020, presents a significant risk to human health, which is a natural and inevitable outcome of the pandemic. As

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well as other penalties, there may be curfews, social isolation, unemployment, travel limitations, and so on. The socioeconomic environment was also impacted to a significant degree. Additional impacts have been caused by this pandemic. According to studies that will be published in 2020 by Adel et al., the effects of COVID-19 seem to anticipate short-, medium-, and long-term implications, and it will take a long time for patients to get relief from their symptoms. To begin, it seems that the tourist, retail, and entertainment industries will be the ones to suffer the most in the short run. According to Nicola et al.'s 2020 research, it is anticipated that automobile, tour-event operators, banking and insurance firms, and energy corporations will all have an impact on air-to-sea transportation in the not-too-distant future, and the consequences of these industries will be seen. In the long term, the scenario, which does not seem to be completely understood at this moment, may have repercussions for economies all around the world. Therefore, in contrast to the governments of many other countries, the government of Turkiye made a number of strategic decisions and carried out a series of activities to address the current socioeconomic, built environment, and other associated concerns in a variety of domains (Ahsan, 2020; Tanrivermis, 2020).

Keywords: *Usd in Turkiye, Gold and Real Estate Price Change in Metropolitans, Usd in the Last 10 Years, Comparison of Gold and Real Estate, Usd, Gold and Real Estate Rates in Metropolitans, Real Estate Price Change in Metropolitans*

Introduction

Because people in Turkiye see housing not only as something they have to have but also as something that may provide them with an income, the housing market is quickly becoming one of the most significant economic sectors in the country. For instance, between the years 2000 and 2018, there was a growth of more than thirty percent in the construction of structures. In addition, the nation intended to construct or remodel around thirteen million housing units, with the goal of constructing one million housing units' year beginning in the year 2020 (TOK, 2020). Before the epidemic and for a few months after it started, the real estate market was characterized by extremism as well as high interest rates. In public banks, the state has lowered lending rates, developed web-based title documents, and offered chances in the private sector such as a restriction

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on dismissal and a short-time working allowance (Tanrivermis, 2020). This was done to cut down on the excessive supply as well as the financial strain that the epidemic was having.

On the other hand, urbanization seems to be a significant risk factor for major repercussions, including the long-term effects of COVID-19, as a result of people and communities living, working, and interacting with one another in close quarters. This is because urbanization places individuals and communities in closer proximity to one another. The decision-making process that individuals go through while deciding between urban and rural settings sheds light on the connection that exists between the COVID-19 epidemic, urbanization, and/or urban density. There are several other classifications that may be used to quantify density, such as population density, residential density, net density, gross density, business density, and other classifications that are quite similar.

Results

The word "density" is being used in the context of this study to refer to "population density." Population density is the term used to describe the density at which an administrative district generally houses an average of one person per square kilometer. On the other side, density has been linked to severe dangers to public health, such as the spread of infectious illnesses (Panwar & Mishra, 2020; Yang, Wang, Zhang, & Ke, 2020). [Panwar & Mishra, 2020; Yang, Wang, Zhang, & Ke, 2020]. More than 95% of all COVID-19 cases have been reported in urban areas, according to research that was released by UN Habitat in April 2020 (UN Habitat, 2020). This study found that the Corona virus has invaded more than 1,430 cities in 210 different nations. It was believed that this was the cause of the Corona virus's widespread distribution. For instance, research conducted in India found that the risk was 1.09 times greater in urban regions and 1.89 times higher in urban slum-like surroundings (as described in Mishra, Gayen, and Haque, 2020 in Swarajya, 2020). These findings were published in the journal Swarajya. Once again, density may occur in locations such as streets, parks, workplaces, residential neighborhoods, industrial neighborhoods, and commercial districts.

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In this instance, the significance of a residential unit's relationship to a specific place within a district is underlined for its relevance. In this environment, individuals are determining whether or not to purchase, as well as choosing between different degrees of service linked to housing, and this particular sort of enhanced housing is vital for health both during and after the COVID-19 epidemic. People are gradually shifting away from apartments and towards detached homes with fewer levels, and the pandemic is training people to foster this enthusiasm (2021). This is because of the rise in population density that has occurred in metropolitan areas as a direct result of the vertical construction of apartment buildings and other types of multi-family homes (Ahsan, 2020). According to study conducted in 2020 by Nicola et al., horizontal construction is picking up speed in the urban edges, in rural regions, and in newly constructed residential zones. At the same time, the relationship between pricing and rental price is shifting in real estate markets as a consequence of a decrease in the building intensity. This is due to the fact that more homes are being rented out rather than built.

Variable elements such as these attract attention to the urban dynamic's viewpoint, which offers a range of opportunities and difficulties. This tendency may be worsened by the ongoing influence of COVID-19 (Avetisyan, 2020), since variable factors such as these bring focus to the urban dynamic's perspective. It was documented that the percentage of people living in urban regions in Turkiye went from 43.78% to 75.14% during 1980-2019 (UN, 2018), and this rate increased significantly (TURKSTAT, 2020a). In addition, the percentage of people living in urban areas increased.

On the other hand, the real estate markets had arrived at a point of equilibrium shortly before the spread of the coronavirus started. On the other side, TURKSTAT 202 expects that the annual rate of home sales in 2020 will be 11.65% higher than it was in 2019, which was the previous year. The real estate and construction industries contribute significantly to Turkiye's GDP. Due to the fact that it provides jobs for nearly 2 million people, it plays a significant leadership role in the economy of the nation (TUIK, 2019b).

In conclusion, the objective of this study was to present an overview of the real estate market in connection to urban dynamics and to propose fundamental solutions for the housing sector in Turkiye throughout the COVID-19 process. Because there has been no prior research conducted

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on this topic as part of academic study, the goals of this study are to (1) fill the void that has been left in academic study and (2) offer light on potential directions for future research. In light of this, it is very necessary that our study places a strong emphasis on the influence that both the housing market and population density have. Fieldwork for this study could not be carried out as planned because of the several curfews that were imposed. The socioeconomic aspects of the area that was researched, in addition to the methodologies used there. As a consequence of this, secondary data were used, with a particular focus placed on the macroeconomic prognosis, the overall status of the real estate market, COVID-19 instances, urban concentration, and the influence that it has on the housing market in cities.

Literature Review

This study focuses on the residential real estate market in Turkiye during the first, second, and third quarters of the year 2020. The scope of this coverage extends to include first-hand house sales, second-hand housing sales, mortgage sales, development permit sales, and acquisitions made by international purchasers. The vast majority of the information used in this investigation came from online portals maintained by several Turkish government agencies, including the Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK), the Central Bank of Turkiye (CBRT), the General Directorate of Land Registry and Cadastre (TKGM), and the Ministry of Health. This study also made use of a variety of secondary sources, such as publications assessed by experts in the field, reports, and newspapers from throughout the country. When it comes to the process of intensification, population figures are the key drivers of the quantity of space that is necessary. The results of this study used data from the 2019 census to conduct an analysis and evaluation of the influence that urbanization has had. Based on the findings of this research, the 10 provinces in Turkiye that have the greatest population density per square kilometer are Istanbul, Ankara, Izmir, Bursa, Antalya, Konya, and Gaziantep. Kocaeli was also included in this list. Bayburt, Tunceli, Ardahan, Gumushane, Artvin, Ankara, Erzincan, Kars, Kastamonu, and Sivas were the 10 provinces that had the lowest population density per square kilometer. Other provinces with low population density per square kilometer were Ardahan, Gumushane, and Artvin. In this context, the pattern of

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home sales in these areas that have been impacted by urbanization has been analyzed to get a deeper comprehension of the consequences of urbanization.

The 10 provinces in Canada are ordered according to their population-weighted densities, starting with the most packed and working their way down to the least populous. Honor, 2020; TurkStat will serve as the primary reference for this research in the year 2020. In recent years, the districts of Istanbul have come under increased scrutiny as a result of Turkiye's high rate of house purchases, Istanbul's economic dominance in comparison to that of other provinces, and Istanbul's lead in terms of population density. These districts were investigated in this research to present a picture of the situation at the local level since the bulk of the population in congested regions is also situated in Istanbul, and 40% of COVID-19 instances have been identified.

To restate, throughout the time period that was being routinely evaluated, the Turkish government did not publish any data on a daily, monthly, or weekly basis that were broken down by province, district, or even city. A picture is built of the many different approaches and policies that the government has put into place regarding urbanization and real estate in order to provide a foundation for a better understanding of the dynamics at play in both markets. TURKSTAT 2019 reports that 59 percent of Turkiye's population lives in their own homes, 25.2 percent in rented homes, and 15.2 percent in other types of housing. On the other hand, in regard to Istanbul's homes in comparison to the other provinces, it contributes a bigger proportion of the total, which comes to 28.6% (TUIK, 2019).

The majority of a person's monthly income goes toward their mortgage or rent, making these costs the greatest component of overall consumer expenditures. In terms of population density, these provinces are also ranked among the top ten most populous provinces in the country. Statistics from 2019 indicate that Istanbul Province has the greatest percentage of the overall Gross Domestic Product (GDP), coming in at 30.7%. After Ankara comes Istanbul, which has a 9.2% share of the market and is the second largest city in Turkiye. Izmir, on the other hand, came in third place with a market share of 6.1%.

The provinces of Istanbul, Ankara, Izmir, Bursa, and Kocaeli have the greatest GDP per capita in dollars, as reported by TUIK 2019 figures. Together, these five provinces account for 53.7% of the

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country's total GDP. On the other side, the provinces of Tunceli, Ardahan, and Bayburt are the ones that contribute the least amount of their respective GDPs to the overall total.

GDP per capita and unemployment rate (in percent) in Turkiye's 10 provinces with the highest and lowest population density, ranked from most populous to least populous. When the relevant provinces are investigated, it is discovered that there is a linear connection between the number of home sales and the GDP per capita in dollars, and it stands to reason that this connection will naturally be mirrored in the urban areas. After Istanbul, the province of Kocaeli has the greatest gross domestic product (\$14,304) per person (TURKSTAT, 2021). On the other hand, it fell behind Ankara, Izmir, and Bursa in terms of home sales; hence, gross domestic product per capita is not the only factor that affects house sales. 3. The findings, together with our understanding of what they mean

Methodology

Concerns of significance pertaining to the Turkish economy Beginning in early June of the year 2020, Turkiye began making the shift back to regular economic circumstances. On the other hand, the Purchasing Managers Index for 2020 indicates that there was a huge drop of 33.4% and 40.90% in April and May of that year, respectively. The substantial rise in July was once again 56.70%, making it the greatest among a number of years' worth of years, suggesting a return to growth. Due to COVID-19, the IMF World Economic Outlook expected that the Turkish economy would contract by an estimated 0.9% in 2019, but forecasted a negative scenario to 5% in 2020, followed by the same growth in 2021 and 5% in 2021. In 2021, the IMF predicted that the economy will expand by the same amount as it did in 2020. It anticipated that the trend would continue higher until (IMF, 2020).

The GDP growth rate in Turkiye has been on a declining trend since 2014, with a GDP growth rate of 9.9% in the second quarter of 2020 (TUIK, 2020c). This is according to the reports. According to the findings of the study that was carried out by the IMF and made public, it is anticipated that the unemployment rate in Turkiye would climb to 17.2% by the end of 2020 and then reduce to 15.6% by the end of 2021. Inflation hit an all-time high of 25.2% in October of 2018, and after finishing the year at 20.3% and beginning the new year at 11.84%, it began a downward trend in

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the months that followed. The lifespan of this model was 15 years. A further forecast that was made in the research indicated that the yearly inflation rate would continue to be nearly comparable to its present level until the end of the year 2020 and until the end of the year 2021. On the other hand, the government anticipates an inflation rate of 8.5% by the end of the year 2020. The current account deficit, which is projected to be 8.0 billion US dollars in 2019, is projected to reduce to 2.9 billion US dollars in 2020, according to the predictions of the International Monetary Fund (IMF). In 2019, the current account deficit is predicted to be. Since 2019, Turkiye's young unemployment rate has been at 26.7%, 12.8% in April, 12.9% in May, 13.4% in June, and 13.4% in July in 2020. This compares to a rate of 12.8% in April, 12.9% in May, 13.4% in June, and 13.4% in July in 2019. This is nearly double the national average unemployment rate of 13.4%, which was recorded in August at 13.2%. In April, it was 12.8%, in May it was 12.9%, in June it was 13.4%, in July it was 13.4%, and in August it was 13.2%. The nation has seen a decrease in employment, with a total of 2.2 million people working in the construction business, mostly as a consequence of the fall in building activity; a picture very similar to this one is also relevant for the tourism and commercial real estate markets (Tanrivermis, 2020).

Findings

Although fewer people were worked in agriculture, the construction industry, and the service sector, the number of people working in the industrial sector climbed somewhat. The fact that the proportionate rate of growth has been falling since 2017 and that unemployment rates have been rising, coupled with the fact that the per capita income in 2019 was \$9042, suggests that macroeconomic indicators are going in the direction of a negative trajectory, and COVID-19 has exacerbated the pressure in this direction. The fact that the city and urbanization can only be defined by law in the Turkish legal system demonstrates that there is a great deal of unfinished business in connection with the idea of urbanization. The phenomena of urbanization have its own unique social, economic, demographic, and physical manifestations; this is due to the fact that the definition of urbanization is based on law that takes into account the number of people living in an area. A systemic issue has emerged as a result of the fast growth and development of urban

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areas, as well as the ongoing rise in the population of the globe. This has led to the proliferation of slum communities.

As a consequence of this, the government of Turkiye came to the conclusion that it needed to create the Turkish Housing Development Administration (TOK). This was done with the goal of resolving housing and urbanization issues on a national scale via the supply of adequate housing that was of a high quality and a positive environment. In addition to this, it gives protection to disadvantaged individuals who are relocating from rural to urban regions in the hope of finding cheaper rentals. In light of this, the Turkish Mass Housing Administration (TOK) has established a goal to construct 100,000 social housing units yearly by the year 2020 (Turkish Mass Housing Administration, 2020).

Both the population density in Turkiye and the mechanism of transmission of COVID-19 demonstrated that the virus is more frequent in the country's urban centers. In Turkiye, the population density is highest. As of the 20th of November in the year 2020, the Ministry of Health in Turkiye reported that 16,937,887 people in Turkiye had been tested for the disease, with 435,273 confirmed cases, 367,592 recoveries, and 12,084 fatalities. On October 30, 2020, the number of patients who were diagnosed with COVID-19 in Istanbul topped 40 percent of the total number of cases throughout the nation. During the COVID-19 process, we saw a rise in the number of private cars on the road, as well as an increase in property values and sales.

During the COVID-19 era in Turkiye, the provinces with the largest population densities are the ones that saw both a decline and a rise in the number of home sales. The months of May and June were particularly hard struck by the economic downturn that began in Turkiye in March 2020 and did not end until October 2020. On the other side, July went through a period of significant improvement in the first decade of this century. Real estate markets have found activity in cities with a high population density such as Istanbul, which is a global city, and in places such as Ankara, Izmir, Kocaeli and Bursa, which have the requirements to become a world city, as well as in cities with the least population density. Istanbul is a global city, while Ankara, Izmir, Kocaeli and Bursa all have the credentials to become a world city. Istanbul and Ankara, respectively, are the provinces that have recorded the largest number of instances of the disease. In terms of population density, Ankara is the sixth biggest province in Turkiye; yet, the city's total number of property sales places

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it in second place, behind only Istanbul. Izmir was placed third in terms of both the total number of property sales and the population density of the city. In spite of the fact that Zonguldak is the tenth most populous province, the percentage of residents who have purchased a home is much lower than in other high-population provinces (Figure 6). On April 10, Turkiye initiated the practice of imposing weekend lockdowns in thirty of its major cities, one of which being Zonguldak. Because Zonguldak is a mining city and has the highest concentration of asthma patients in the region, this decision was made there. Despite this, real estate sales were down 19% from the first quarter of 2020 to the second quarter of the same year.

The fact that the economic situation in these provinces is much better than the economic situation in other provinces in Turkiye demonstrates that it has a favorable influence on the number of dwellings, as may be said in this context. real estate sales and urbanization. Because of the much larger population density in these regions, this is the situation that has arisen. The difference between nominal and real data is fairly large; yet, inflation-adjusted dwelling price rise for the year leading up to November 2022 was quite strong, coming in at 57.2%. This is despite the fact that nominal statistics are far more accurate than actual data. The price of property in Turkiye's main cities rose by 193.9% between November 2021 and November 2022, reaching 26,904 TL (1.432 USD) per square meter on average. The costliest property market in Turkiye may be found in Istanbul, which is also the biggest city in the nation. M. After taking into account the impact of inflation, the price of a home increased by 59.4% over the previous year. The average price of a property in Ankara, the capital city of the nation, grew by an astonishing 195.9% year on year in November 2022, reaching 12,446 TL (\$663 USD) per square meter. This figure represents a year-on-year growth of the price of a house.

Prices of homes have climbed by a cumulative 60.5% over the last year when inflation is taken into account. Izmir is the third biggest city in the nation, and in November 2022, the price of housing reached 20,861 TL (US\$ 1,110) per square meter on an annual basis. This is a price increase of 64.3% when adjusted for inflation. M. Prices of newly constructed houses climbed by 164.5 percent year over year in November 2022, while prices of previously owned homes jumped by 176.4 percent (or 49.9% adjusted for inflation), according to data collected by the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD). The level of demand for houses and other types of properties is rather stable. The eleven-month period of 2022 saw a total of 1.28 million

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home sales, as reported by the Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK). This represents a minor rise of 1% in comparison to the same period of the previous year. This followed a decrease of 0.5% for the year 2021. According to the figures that were released by TURKSTAT, the number of dwellings acquired by foreign purchasers in Turkiye in the first eleven months of 2022 grew from 50,735 to 61,104 in the same time. This is an increase over the previous year's figure of 50,735.

This was the highest ever recorded number of sales for homes purchased by individuals from foreign nations. Because of the sustained unconventional monetary policy implemented by the central bank, the value of the Turkish lira increased by nearly 69% during the course of the last three years, from a rate of 5.85 TL to 1 USD in December 2019 to a rate of 18.66 TL to 1 USD in December 2022. He misplaced his

Rate Reduction in the Face of Rising Prices and Trade Imbalances

It's possible that this will encourage more people to buy products and services from other countries. Many buyers from the Gulf area have entered the real estate market as a result of the very low pricing in the market. This is due to the devaluation of the currency. Following yearly expansions of 11.4% in 2021, 1.9% in 2020, 0.8% in 2019 and 3% in 2018, the Turkish economy increased by about 5% in 2022. This growth followed expansions of 11.4% in 2021, 1.9% in 2020, 0.8% in 2019 and 3% in 2018. Strong investment, production, and exports all contributed to this increase to a significant extent. Although projections for this year indicate that there would be a deceleration in economic development, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) anticipates a modest rise of 3%. This projection is somewhat more optimistic than the World Bank's growth prediction of 2.7%. The level of demand is quite consistent. The demand for real estate in Turkiye remains relatively consistent, as shown by the fact that the total number of home sales reached 1.28 million in the first eleven months of 2022, representing a marginal rise of 1% in comparison to the same time period in the year before. According to Turkstat, there will be a decrease of 0.5% in the next year. This followed a decrease of 0.5 percent in 2021. Property transactions in Turkiye During the same time period, the number of new homes sold in Turkiye fell by 0.7% as compared to the same period the previous year, reaching a total of 382,190. Turkiye had a growth of 1.7%, bringing the total

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number of units to 895,469 units. There is also a substantial geographical imbalance, with demand in Turkiye's smaller rural regions rising in favor of demand in Turkiye's bigger cities. This trend can be seen across Turkiye.

17% of all sales in the first eleven months of 2022 amounted to 222,910 units. This is a 6% drop as compared to the same period in the previous year. The number of homes that were bought and sold in Ankara decreased by 10.5% year on year, reaching 109,801 units and accounting for around 9% of the national market share. Izmir had a little fall in housing sales year on year, which accounts for around 6% of the market. Additionally, the number of homes sold in Izmir fell by 1%, bringing the total number of homes sold to 72,626. When compared to the previous year, housing sales in Bursa had a 2.1% rise, bringing the total number of units sold to 46,583. This represents 3.6% of the market overall. When compared to the previous year, the number of homes that were sold in Antalya climbed by 22.6%, bringing the total to 69,291 units and giving the city a market share of 5.4% over the period of January through November 2022. The number of international purchasers of property in Turkiye increased to 61,104 in the first eleven months of the year 2022. TURKSTAT. This was the highest ever recorded number of sales for homes purchased by individuals from foreign nations. With the exception of 2016 and 2020, when sales of real estate to foreign purchasers are expected to decrease due to the pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus, Turkiye is seeing an increase in real estate sales to international buyers. The significant uptick in tourism from the Gulf area has led to a rise in the number of foreign purchasers investing significant sums of money in real estate in Turkiye. The weakening of the Turkish lira has led to an increase in the number of tourists that come to the country. Because Arabic is spoken at a good number of Istanbul's shops and eateries, visitors to the city may get the impression that they are in a major city in the Gulf area. This is due to the fact that Istanbul is becoming an increasingly popular tourism destination among Arab nations. The number of homes acquired by individuals from other countries increased by a factor of more than four between 2016 and 2021, going from 18,391 to 58,576. During this time period, purchases made by Russians, Iranians, and Iraqis each accounted for almost a third of the total amount spent by purchasers from other countries.

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Leadership of Foreign Real Estate Buyers in Turkiye

They also have a strong sense of cultural connection to the nation. In spite of this, Russians took the dominant position among foreign purchasers of real estate in Turkiye during the first eleven months of 2022, accounting for around 22.5% of the market share. When compared to the proportion of shares owned by Iraqis, Iranians had a 12.2% stake in the company, while Iraqis held a 9.5% stake. As a direct response to the rise in the number of Russian guests visiting Turkiye, financial institutions in that country have begun to offer accounts denominated in rubles. The vast majority of purchasers were individuals from other countries, and their transactions accounted for nearly forty percent of the overall sales in Istanbul between January and November of 2022. After this came Antalya, which accounts for 32 percent of the total sales, followed by Mersin, Ankara, and Ankara, each of which accounts for 6 percent. Bursa came in at 4.2%, while Bursa came in at 3%. Relaxing limits on the ownership of homes by non-citizens by the year 2002, the Turkish real estate market has been accessible for the first time to buyers from other countries. However, they were only permitted to purchase real estate in a limited region. Furthermore, in accordance with the "reciprocity clause," they could only do so if they were residents of countries that gave reciprocal rights to Turkish nationals. These nations were the United Kingdom, Germany, and the Netherlands. They were given permission to purchase properties. The areas were done away with in 2005, but the practice of reciprocity has maintained since then. As of the month of August 2012, the reciprocity restriction has been formally removed, which means that people of 183 more countries now have the legal right to acquire real estate in Turkiye. As a result of the relaxation of the reciprocity requirements, people of nations like as China, Russia, and India, in addition to those from Gulf Arab states, are now permitted to enter the country. The previous limit of 2.5 hectares has been expanded to 33 hectares, making it possible for non-citizens to acquire far larger tracts of property without being required to get any specialized permissions. Tens of thousands of people who are not Turkish nationals have been given the opportunity to buy property in Turkiye. The majority of these purchases have been made in the Marmara and Mediterranean areas, which are among the most significant financial and tourist hubs in Turkiye. The rule, which made it easier for non-Turkish citizens to meet the requirements for Turkish citizenship, made the Turkish lira more volatile in comparison to other currencies, and the fact that non-Turkish nationals were free from paying VAT led to a rise in overall sales. Additionally helpful was the volatility of the Turkish lira in comparison to other currencies.

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Since January 2017, Turkiye has been offering citizenship to non-Turkish nationals via a variety of pathways. One of these pathways is the purchase of real estate in the country that is valued at a minimum of one million dollars in US currency. The Land Registry's title charges were decreased from 2% to 1.5% in the same year that the government announced further steps to entice overseas purchasers to purchase real estate. Each party, the buyer and the seller, is responsible for paying these costs, bringing the whole sum to around 3%. Owners of homes in Turkiye who do not make their primary residence in the country are free from paying value-added tax (VAT) on such homes if the purchase price was made in a currency other than the Turkish lira. Buyers of homes are expected to keep possession of the property for a period of one year after the purchase date. In the beginning of this year, the stamp duty on "promise-to-sale contracts" was lowered from 0.95 percent to 0 percent. In September of 2018, new legislation was enacted that brought to a reduction in the needed amount of financial commitment to get Turkish citizenship. To be more specific, the previous requirements for gaining citizenship have been reduced to just buying a piece of real estate worth at least \$250,000. Or maintaining a balance of at least half a million dollars in a bank account in Turkiye for a period of at least three years; it is necessary to create at least fifty jobs, which is a decrease from the former maximum of one hundred jobs. On the other hand, starting of the 13th of June in 2022, the minimum barrier raised from two hundred fifty thousand dollars to four hundred thousand dollars. This took place at a period in which there was a rising interest, on a global scale, in purchasing property in Turkiye.

The activity level in the residential building industry is beginning to level down. According to the data that was supplied by TURKSTAT, the total number of homes in housing structures that were granted building permits in Turkiye during the first three quarters of 2022 was 13.9 percent lower than it was during the same time period in the previous year. It dropped to a total of 413,639 units. Turkiye issued building permits for a total of 34,310 single-family homes during the first three quarters of the year 2022. When compared to the same time period in the prior year, this represents a decline of 5.8 percent. There were 16,515 homes that were two-family homes, which is 19.3 percentage points fewer than there were a year earlier. When compared to the previous year, there was a 14.3% drop, resulting in the total number of residential units in structures containing three or more dwellings coming in at 362,814. After dropping by 52.2% in 2019 and 52.4% in 2018, the number of residential construction permits is expected to record a considerable rise of 30.2% in

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2021 and 73.8% in 2020. This comes after the number of residential building permits dropped by 52.2% in 2019 and 52.4% in 2018. The returns on rentals in Istanbul might vary anywhere from average to very good. The profits on rentals in Turkiye fall somewhere between modest and satisfactory. The findings of a study that was conducted by Global Property Guide in November 2022 indicate that the gross rental returns for apartments in Istanbul range anywhere from 2.53% to 12.72%, with an average of 5.99%. This is the return on the purchase price of a rental property before any taxes, vacancy charges, or other expenditures are taken into account.

Rental returns in other cities are, on average, about the same as they are in Istanbul, which is a significant difference. Returns on rental investments in Ankara are anywhere from 4.05% to 11.41% of the entire amount. Returns on rentals in Antalya might vary anywhere from 3.66 percent to 7.99 percent annually. The returns on rentals in Izmir range anywhere from 3.69% to 13.42%. There is a wide range of potential gross rental returns in Adana, ranging from 2.92% to 6.98%. Rental returns in Bursa might range anywhere from 3.31 percent to 7.00 percent of the property's purchasing price. Kayseri yields varied between 4.77% and 7.15%. There is a range of potential gross rental returns in Konya, ranging from 4.48% to 6.88%.

The yearly report of the Turkish housing index has been made available for public consumption by the Central Bank of the Republic of Turkiye. According to the findings of the study, the nation is in the midst of one of the most severe crises over real estate it has ever encountered. The bank said that the average price of a home in Istanbul reached 1.6 million TL (\$110,000) in 2022, reflecting a significant increase from the price of 750,000 TL recorded in the previous year. The data that was supplied by the bank indicated that the annual valuation rate of real estate values across Turkiye reached an average of 96.4 percent in the month of February, while in Istanbul, this rate reached 106.3 percent. Even in places with a majority Kurdish population, such as Diyarbakir and Sanliurfa in the southeast of the nation, where the region is often regarded to be the least developed section of the country, growth was 111 percent.

Inflation, growing building costs, and an imbalance between supply and demand are highly major aspects in the issue of rising real estate prices in Turkiye, according to the opinions of specialists. As a direct consequence of this, both rent and housing prices shot through the roof. Middle East

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Eye published an article in September 2021 stating that the cost of one ton of cement was \$500 at the time. The cost of one ton of cement is around 1,400 liras, which is equivalent to approximately 95 dollars.

The building industry saw negative repercussions as a direct consequence of the persistent increase in commodity prices brought on by Russia's takeover of Ukraine. For instance, the cost of a ton of rebar rose from around 745 dollars in April of the previous year to 15,000 liras. This is a significant increase in cost. Dramatic surge in prices the capacity of people in the middle class to purchase houses has been significantly impacted as a result of considerable price hikes. The rising disparity between the producer pricing index (PPI) and the consumer price index (CPI), which factors in the price of goods like food, power, and transportation, is another major factor. This demonstrates very clearly that the rise in home prices is nearly exactly twice as high as the rise in salaries that are sufficient to keep up with inflation.

Anger towards outsiders Another crisis was generated when hundreds of Turkish governments started asking on social media to repatriate refugees, block the entrance of new migrants, and restrict the selling of property to foreigners in response to the crisis in the real estate market. At the moment, Turkiye will issue citizenship to any foreigner who purchases property in the country. Over the course of the previous nine years, there have been 293,000 sales of houses to foreign buyers totaling \$41.3 billion. Because of this rising antipathy against migrants, the government was obliged to announce that it would be changing its stance.

Recent Events in Ukraine

The defenders of Ukraine have advanced to the next stage of their struggle to free their country's sovereign regions from Russian dominance. This next phase of the conflict will take place in eastern Ukraine.

The two percent target is a floor, not a ceiling, and we are willing to spend that additional spending to ensure that our collective defense is credible and to continue to upgrade the capabilities of the alliance. Now that this has been brought to your attention, it is important that Finland will be attending this year's NATO summit as a member of the alliance for the very first time. we need Additionally, it will assist us in enhancing the interoperability of NATO, standardizing

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fundamental weaponry, and bolstering our military industrial bases. All of these initiatives are, at this moment, components of the fundamental reform on collective defense and deterrence that NATO leaders agreed on at the Madrid Summit a year ago. This summit took place in Spain.

Turkiye in General

In addition to being a member of the E7, EAGLEs, and NICs, Turkiye was one of the first countries to join both the OECD and the G20. The Turkish economy is the 19th biggest economy in the world as of 2023 according to the ranking of nominal GDP; however, according to the ranking of PPP, the Turkish economy is the 11th largest economy in the world. According to the classifications used by the International Monetary Fund, Turkiye is a developing economy with upper-middle-income levels and mixed markets.[40] Agricultural goods, textiles, motor vehicles, transportation equipment, construction materials, consumer electronics, and home appliances are just some of the items that this nation is one of the biggest manufacturers of in the world. The nominal gross domestic product of Turkiye achieved an all-time high of \$1.029 trillion in the year 2023, while the nominal gross domestic product per capita of the nation hit an all-time high of \$12,489 in the year 2013.

In the year 2023, the GDP (PPP) of Turkiye hit a new high of \$3.5 trillion, while the GDP per capita (PPP) of the nation increased to \$41,412 in the same year. The recent drop in estimates for Turkiye's nominal gross domestic product that are based on the US dollar may be substantially ascribed to the devaluation of the Turkish lira, notably during the Turkish currency and debt crisis that lasted from 2018-2022. The economic crisis was a significant contributor to this reduction. In the early 2020s, persistently rising inflation is a problem that must be solved before it can be considered a worry.

There have been substantial advances in the financial and social elements of the Turkish economy in the previous 20 years, such as the growth in employment and the average salary since the year 2000. One example of these developments is the rise in the number of people working in Turkiye. The increase in the size of Turkiye's middle class is one illustration of these trends. Recent events have resulted in a deceleration in the rate of growth of the Turkish economy. This is the outcome of substantial changes in both internal and foreign causes, as well as a decline in the quantity of

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economic reforms enacted by the Turkish government. Both of these factors have contributed to this conclusion. There is a school of thought among ecologists that contends the economy is dependent, to an excessive degree, on the building and contracting industries. According to data provided by Eurostat, Turkiye's GDP per capita in 2018 was equal to 64% of the average for the EU when purchasing power parity was taken into account.

Turkiye has the lowest proportion of its people actively engaging in the labor force of any OECD country, with just 61.5% of the population doing so. The median rate for OECD nations is 78%. More than 5,000 people with high net worth (HNWIs, defined as having a net worth of at least \$1 million) departed Turkiye in 2017, marking the second year in a row that this has taken place.

The low rate of saving that has been characteristic of the Turkish economy throughout its entire history has remained mostly unchanged.[50]

Conclusion

Since 2004, the level of Turkiye's public debt stock has stayed under the "60% Maastricht criterion" that was established by the EU. This accomplishment was first completed in the year 2004. In a similar manner, the budget deficit was able to achieve one of the Maastricht requirements for the budget by decreasing from more than 10% to less than 3% between the years 2002 and 2011. The international credit rating agency Moody's Investors Service raised Turkiye's credit rating by one notch in January 2010, making it one notch higher than it was before. The credit rating agency Fitch raised Turkiye's credit rating to investment grade in 2012, after an absence of 18 years during which it had not been raised. After this, a rating increase was issued by the credit rating agency Moody's Investors Service in May 2013, just before the service was terminated. The ratings on Turkiye's government bonds have dropped to the lowest level possible for investment grade. Turkiye received its first investment grade rating from Moody's in the last two decades with this announcement. In an official statement, the rating agency said that the country's "recent and expected future improvements in key economic indicators" were the basis for the warning of a downgrade. In Turkiye, the price of an average share of stock almost and precisely doubled in 2009. On May 10, 2017, the major index of the Turkish stock market, the Borsa Istanbul (BIST-100 Index), reached an all-time high with 95,735 points, so setting a new

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record and surpassing its previous best. As of the 5th of January in 2018, the index has hit 116,638 points. On the other hand, as a consequence of the currency rate and debt crises that occurred in Turkiye in 2018, the index once again dropped below 100,000 in May. Since the beginning of the worldwide financial crisis in 2008, the BIST-100 Index reached its lowest level in dollar terms at the beginning of June this year.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) forecasted in 2017 that the Turkish economy would have an average annual growth rate of 4.9% for the period of 2015-2025, making Turkiye one of the OECD nations with the fastest expanding economy. In May of 2018, Moody's Investors Service reassessed its projection for the expansion of the Turkish economy, bringing it down from 4% to 2.5% for the current year and from 3.5% to 2% for the next year.

According to a special study that the Financial Times published on Turkiye in 2013, corporate executives and government officials in Turkiye believed that expanding outside conventional western markets was the quickest way to increase exports. When compared to the previous year, when Turkiye was responsible for more than half of its total exports, the European Union accounted for little more than a third of Turkiye's total exports in 2013. This is a major reduction from the previous year. In spite of this, by the year 2018, the rate of exports to the EU has once again surpassed the 50% threshold. According to the Foreign Investment Index for 2017, the amount of money that companies located in Turkiye have transferred to other countries has grown by a factor of 10 over the course of the previous 15 years. According to figures that were made public by the government of Turkiye in December 2022, the annual inflation rate in the nation hit an all-time high of 85.51% in the month of October. The Federal Reserve Bank of the United States decreased interest rates in response to increasing prices; nonetheless, this outcome was somewhat below the expectations that were set. Since the value of the lira began to decline in November of the previous year, inflation has change up to unprecedented levels. This occurred not long after the Turkish central bank had begun cutting interest rates as part of the easing cycle that Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan has been working on for some time. Recep Tayyip Erdogan's fixation on preserving low inflation rates was ultimately put to rest in June 2023, when Turkiye's first female central bank governor hiked the benchmark interest rate from 8.5% to 15%. This marked the beginning of the end for Erdogan's preoccupation with preserving low inflation rates.

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If a generalization is made regarding the comparison of the rates of change in the prices of Usd, gold and real estate in the metropolitan cities in the last 10 years in Turkiye, the mid-June 2023 period (the period after the election) Usd and gold increases are not yet reflected in the housing prices, and the prices of Usd and gold in the previous period are not taken into account. Considering this, while the Average Housing Sales Price in Turkiye was approximately 135.000 TL on 1 June 2013, this value reached approximately 1.635.000 TL on 1 June 2023. Again for the same period, USD, which was 1,8904 TL, reached 20,8215 TL. Gram gold, on the other hand, rose from 80 TL to 1.335 TL.

While the percentage increase in housing prices in metropolitan areas was higher than in Turkey in general, this rate reached even higher values in Istanbul. While it is observed that the average price of a house in Istanbul 10 years ago, in USD basis, has increased by approximately 25% on USD basis, it has been observed that it has lost approximately 25% in value when a gold-based evaluation is made. However, it should not be overlooked that the house will also bring in similar rates (about 25% and above, depending on the region) for 10 years on average.

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